

THE DIFFICULTIES OF TRANSLATING ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGY IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *Sometimes it is said that the translations of english phrases and idioms can be different in uzbek language. In such cases, pupils often have problems to translate them properly, so this article is devoted to analyse such challenges happened during the translation into our own language English language is not so difficult to learn and to translate, however because of rich vocabulary now and then learners have to comprehend those phraseologies with suitable translation as far as they understood.*

Key words: *phraseology, phrases, idioms, archaism, expressions, translation challenges, voluminous, speech equality, suitable meaning, phraseological unit, Literature skills, competences, vividness bilingual knowledge, phraseological sentences, let the cat out of her basket, leg and arm*

Annotatsiya: *ba'zan inglizcha ibora va idiomalarning tarjimalari o'zbek tilida turlicha bo'lishi mumkinligi aytiladi. Bunday hollarda, o'quvchilar ko'pincha to'g'ri, ularni tarjima qilish muammolar bor, shuning uchun bu maqola bunday muammolar o'z tiliga tarjima paytida sodir tahlil bag'ishlangan ingliz tili o'rganish va tarjima qilish juda qiyin emas, biroq, chunki boy so'z hozir va keyin o'quvchilar mos tarjima bilan o'sha frazeologiyalarni tushunmoq kerak. ular tushunganidek.*

Kalit so'zlar: *frazeologiya, iboralar, idiomalar, arxaizm, iboralar, tarjima muammolari, hajmli, nutq tengligi, mos ma'no, frazeologik birlik, adabiy ko'nikma, malakalar, jonli ikki tilli bilim, frazeologik jumlar, mushukni savatidan, oyog'idan va qo'lidan chiqarsin.,*

Аннотация: *Иногда говорят, что переводы английских фраз и идиом на узбекском языке могут отличаться. В таких случаях у учеников часто возникают проблемы с их правильным переводом, поэтому эта статья посвящена анализу таких проблем, возникающих при переводе на наш родной язык Английский язык не так сложно выучить и перевести, однако из-за богатого словарного запаса время от времени учащимся приходится понимать эти фразеологизмы с подходящим переводом, а также насколько они понимали.*

Ключевые слова: *фразаология, фразы, идиомы, архаизм, выражения, трудности перевода, объемный, равенство речи, подходящее значение,*

фразеологизм, литературные навыки, компетенции, живость двуязычных знаний, фразеологические предложения, выпустить кошку из корзины, нога и рука.,

In any language there are certain expressions that are understood by representatives of certain nationalities. Such sentence turns are called idioms or phraseological units. It is impossible to divide them into components, idioms should be perceived not as a separate set of words, but as a whole. They can not change the order of incoming units and word forms.

Such phrases will help make the speaker's speech more vivid, voluminous and rich. Knowledge of phraseological units makes foreigners almost "own" people in the eyes of their native language.

Without knowing the exact meaning or equivalent in the native language, it is often difficult to guess the meaning of the expression. Words that are included in the idiom are not related to the meaning of the expression at all.

There are thousands of phrases in English. Of course, they do not need to learn all of them, and not all of them in life will not have a hand. But in order to improve your language level, you need to have at least one of the phraseological units that you most often meet. Our experienced teachers in the language school class "Capital School Center" will tell you about the most common phrases and help you quickly memorize useful phrases.

Idioms can often be confused with proverbs, phraseological verbs and other fixed phrases. Even specialists do not always come to the limit between them.

Idiom refers to the formula tilni ("speech template"), this group also includes prefixes, congratulations and wishes, proverbs and proverbs, phraseological verbs, fixed phrases and verbal word combinations. Therefore, in the reference books there may be inconsistencies, and another phrase becomes a phrase.

At the lessons of our capital School Centre, we memorize many speech models that help in everyday life. How are you? Phrases like. or not an idiom for a moment and they have a direct meaning (translation) of the words in it. Without the use of such strict phrases, it is impossible to start speaking in a foreign language and understand the interlocutor.

Use of phraseological units

Unstressed phrases (phraseological units) are used in informal communication and have a stylistic meaning in a particular social or age group. In business communication and official communication, they are non-existent. Idioms themselves are not so common in everyday speech, for example, verbal vocabulary and phraseological verbs, as we know, belong to the same group of

formulated languages. We often hear phrases such as (from time to time) or search (search) in speech. In our capital School Center, teachers give you the most commonly used phrases in conversation. Once you learn them, you do not have to think about building them.

Why you should know them

Why do we need these stable verbal combinations?

First, native speakers use them in everyday life, that is, foreigners may not understand the meaning of what is being said. Also phraseological units are often three in books or films.

Secondly, this phrase enriches your speech, makes it colorful and shows you erudition in the eyes of the interlocutor.

Third, it will help to better understand the culture and characteristics of people, especially if you study the history of the origin of this or that phraseological unit.

From quatrain, to learn unchangeable phrases and to search for similarities with the native language is just an interesting activity.

How to remember?

When talking to native speakers, you do not hear a lot of English phrases. A foreign person, trying to facilitate his speech, divides complex sentences into several simple sentences and does not use jargon to facilitate understanding. So why should you teach them? - ask that. The answer is simple - it's interesting in the first place. It is not necessary to memorize many unstressed phrases, it is enough to know 2-3 general phraseological units or at least understand the meaning of what is said, even if you do not use them in life.

It will not be difficult to remember at the level of understanding unchangeable phrases, because they contain vivid images, and often behind such a phraseological unit there is a whole interesting story about its appearance.

To remember well, you need to understand its meaning and know how this or that phrase appeared. For example, an interesting story is associated with such a popular and unusual-sounding phrase. Cats and dogs are raining (cats and dogs are raining). Agree, if you translate literally, it turns out to be absolutely nonsense, but there are explanations of this phrase, and not even one. We translate into Russian with the phrase "pour out of a bucket".

One of the most popular versions of its origin is the story of the roof on the roof. Previously, on the roofs of village houses there was a somon, where local cats liked to relax. But strong rain washed them from time to time.

Where to find these phrases in English? A simple vocabulary with a word translation is not suitable for this. The most convenient way to find the right phrase is to use specialized online resources. If English is not your first language, then you will often encounter strange phrases that will confuse you.

These are phraseological units, which are called idioms. Idioms are an integral part of the communication of English-speaking people and are sometimes used more often than phraseological units of the Russian language.

What are phraseological units?

Phraseologies. Stable combinations of words that are not translated in the same way. Precise emotional manipulation phrases. Because of the unusual, these phrases are easy to remember.

the mistake of beginners in language learning is an attempt to literally translate this phrase, as a result of which it often turns out to be nonsense. Idioms can not be translated literally, it is also necessary to take into account that some idiomatic expressions violate the rules of grammaticism and are archaism. It is impossible not to notice that idioms exist not only in English, but also in all other languages, and often inherit the meaning of expression from each other.

Frequent use of phraseologies makes it difficult to use the English language, but makes it more beautiful and lively.

How to start understanding English by ear?

The study of idioms is mandatory for those who want to read literature or watch movies in their original language

Why study idioms?

First, the study of idioms enriches your speech considerably, which is very important for live communication, because phrases can often be found in films and literature, which gives a Passive Plus for watching movies, reading books and comics in the original language.

If you have already started to learn English seriously and for a long time, then you can not bypass the study of phrases, so we have collected the most interesting, Phraseologies are used to express a situation in which you can enjoy two different things at the same time. For example, if you live on the outskirts of the city and you need very little time to get to the city, you can say that you will enjoy the best of both worlds: the tranquillity of the surrounding city and the vibrant city life.

How to successfully work with English idioms.

Let's all look at some popular phrases that we often use in our Russian speech, that is, sooner or later we want to know them in English.

In fact, most often it is necessary not only to translate, but also to find the English equivalent of our Russian opinion. We have all our "Apple and apple trees" together with "buried dogs" in all languages. You just need to know exactly how the foreigner will say it.

Russian word combination fight like a fish on our English equivalent to pull the cat out of its tail to be in the seventh heaven, or to be in the seventh heaven, act stupidly

Stupid is written with a fork on the playing waterhas it's all in the air

Stay in this weather

He waited for the shoes of the Dead Men keep from the nose (rub someone's fur) drawing wool on someone else's eyes like an opener hungry (hungry as a wolf) to make mountains from molehill to make mountains from molehill money does not bite (drowning in insects, swimming in gold) to make money went to the heel of Ruhr his heart sank the stars from the are not enough, and (he) does not set fire to the Thames, or did the fly bite you? What toothed it? Make sure that your nose is as simple as two or four eggs or eggs, to in a sack, to in a poke, poured like a butterfly, to feed the dogs and dogs, to the small world, say that this little world has come from your own hands, to say a shovel, pour out from the bottom to the empty,

(lit.: "Later - alligator", the rhyming answer to the word "later") it's like two drops of water, we like peas kill two birds with one stone kill two birds with one stone to beat around the bush about the bird. An integral part of everyday English is English idioms, proverbs and proverbs. They are very common in written and spoken English. Idioms are usually literally not accepted. To understand this layer of language, it is necessary to familiarize yourself with the meaning and use of each specific idiom. At first glance, this may seem a tedious task, but it is very interesting to learn idioms, especially if you compare English idioms with phraseological units in your native language.

If you learn to use common idioms and phrases, you will be able to speak fluently in English. Learn a few of these phrases, they will definitely be useful. The tables below summarize the most common idioms in American English. You can start by learning the most common English idioms, because when you watch American movies or TV shows, or when you travel to the United States, you will meet them on a regular basis. Once you have mastered them, you can proceed. None of the idioms in this list are rarely encountered or old-fashioned, so you can use any of them with English speakers from all countries where English is spoken. you can find a lot of idioms in the list of English-speaking countries.

English idioms-this is an interesting, interesting part of the language, but sometimes beginners pay too much attention to it. From this article, you will learn what idioms are, whether they are worth studying, what is the difference between idioms and what, and also where do butterflies appear in oshqoz and what kind of spoon it is, suck out of fear. .

What are idioms?

Idioms or phraseological units - these are stable turns of speech, integral combinations of words, as a rule, are understood in a figurative sense. The meaning of the whole phrase is not determined by the meaning of the words that make up it. Often it is difficult to guess the meaning of the idiom, to understand from the words included in it, if you are not familiar with it.

For example: to be in the same boat. It literally means: "to be in a boat", but the meaning of the idiom is different: "to be in the same situation, to experience the same difficulties".

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